

Global trends in climate change litigation: 2023 snapshot

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Joana Setzer and Rebecca Byrnes
Policy report
July 2019

Global trends in climate change litigation: 2020 snapshot

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Policy report
July 2020

Global trends in climate change litigation: 2021 snapshot

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Policy report
July 2021

Global trends in climate change litigation: 2022 snapshot

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Policy report
June 2022

Case numbers rising year on year

- Over 2,340 cases
 - 1,590 in the US
- 2/3 since the Paris Agreement
- 190 cases in the last 12 months
- 2021 highest annual number of cases

Note: Up to end of May 2023, based on Sabin Center databases

Climate litigation continues to spread to new jurisdictions

Number of climate litigation cases around the world, per jurisdiction (up to 31 May 2023)

51 countries

7 new jurisdictions:
 Bulgaria (2021), China (2016), Finland (2022), Romania (2023), Russia (2022), Thailand (2022), and Turkey (2021)

135 cases in the Global South

+ 50 cases before 11 International and regional courts, UN Treaty Bodies and the UNFCCC compliance committee

The number of strategic cases continues to grow

Not all strategic litigation is aligned with climate goals – e.g. ‘ESG backlash’ litigation

Proportion of strategic cases over time (%), outside the US, to 31 May 2023

Strategic cases increasing in numbers and diversity

Climate-aligned

Government framework (80+)

Failure to adapt (14)

Corporate framework (17)

Polluter pays (17)

Integrating climate considerations (206)

Climate-washing (57)

Turning off the taps (28)

Personal responsibility (8)

Global guidance (4)

Just transition cases

Distributional impacts of policies

Challenge JT policies

Non-climate-aligned

Regulatory powers

Stranded assets

SLAPPs

Corporate cases: more sectors and legal arguments

Number of cases against corporations by sector type including US and Global cases (2015–2022)

Future trends

- Litigation focused on the biodiversity-climate nexus
- Duties of governments and corporations to protect the ocean
- Litigation arising from extreme weather events where climate change is not the central focus
- Cases concerning short-lived climate pollutants
- International litigation between states

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Thank you!

- **Access the 2023 report**

<https://www.lse.ac.uk/granthaminstitute/publication/global-trends-in-climate-litigation-2023-snapshot>

- **Access the database:**

<https://climate-laws.org>

- **Contact us:**

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